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STK16 functions in compensatory kinase signaling in response to ERBB2 inhibition.

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We studied signaling dynamics as a system following disruption of a growth factor signal using a growth factor inhibitor. We discovered activation of STK16 in cells exposed to chemical inhibition of HER2. STK16 activation was observed in both prostate cancer and breast cancer cells following pharmacologic inhibition of ERBB2. The origin of STK16 in programmed compensatory responses in cancer is not yet understood.